

Effect of hydrostatic pressure on Transport properties of Mn-site doped

$\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1-x}\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.03, 0.05$) manganites

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Abstract

The basic character of manganites is mainly due to double exchange (DE) between Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} , and this could be modified by doping at A and/or Mn site of the main compounds [1]. We have investigated the transport properties of $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1-x}\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_3$ (0.03 and 0.05) compounds under hydrostatic pressure up to ~ 2.5 GPa. At ambient pressure, $x=0.03$ sample exhibits insulator to semiconducting transition around 100 K, whereas $x=0.05$ sample exhibits insulator to metallic transition around 100 K. It suggests that the enhancement of conductivity through the partial substitution of Mo by Mn, and destroys the charge-ordering (CO) semi conducting phase which induces the metallic transition in $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{MnO}_3$ at low temperatures. However, the appearance of thermal irreversibility between cooling and warming cycles in both samples suggest the first-order transition, and hence possesses the phase transformation in accordance with latent heat [2]. The pressure on both samples further reduces the resistivity down to low temperature 4K. At the same time, pressure suppresses the hysteresis between cooling and warming cycles of both samples, which leads to change from first-order to second-order transition without change in transition temperatures..

ρ vs T under various P of $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1-x}\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x=0.03$) ρ vs T under various P of $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1-x}\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x=0.05$)

References:

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